

NIR Spectroscopy for Engine Oil Characterisation

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Engine (or motor) oil is a lubricant used in internal combustion engines, produced by the blending of 80% (w/w) base oil and 20% (w/w) different additives¹. The American Petroleum Institute (API) has categorized base oils into five categories²; the first three groups are mineral stocks, refined from crude oil with different processes, Group IV is full synthetic (polyalphaolefin), and Group V is for all other base oils not included in Groups I through IV. To date, it is possible to identify the base oil of a lubricant only by looking at the combination of physical properties (such as viscosity index, density, colour, flash point, pour point, aniline point, thermal stability), but the measurement of these parameters is expensive and time consuming. The aim of the present study was to investigate, for the first time, the capability of near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy as a low-cost, green, and nondestructive method in order to identify the type of base oil in engine oil. In order to reach this goal, 53 pure base oils, belonging to different API groups, and 43 engine oils were analysed without any pretreatments.

NIR spectra were acquired in transmittance mode with an FT-NIR spectrophotometer (Buchi NIRFlex N-500) in the 4000–10000 cm⁻¹ range and 4 cm⁻¹ resolution, using a quartz cuvette with 10 mm pathlength.

Principal component analysis performed on the NIR spectra (as the average of 3 spectra) showed that samples form clusters according to their API groups and so to their chemical composition. Thanks to the interesting results obtained in PCA, PLS-DA, as a multivariate classification tool, was applied in order to distinguish among different API groups; satisfactory results were achieved: the prediction abilities in the external test set, composed of 20% randomly selected samples, was 87%.

Keywords: NIR spectroscopy, lubricants, base oil, classification, PLS-DA

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REFERENCES

Leslie RR (2006) Synthetics, mineral oils, and bio based lubricants. CRC Press Taylor & Francis Group

American Petroleum Institute (2012) Engine Oil Licensing and Certification System Seventeenth Edition. 201